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Theory**

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A NUMERICAL FUNCTION IN CONGRUENCE THEORY

In this article we define a function L which will allow us to generalize (separately or simultaneously) some theorems from Numbers Theory obtained by Wilson, Fermat, Euler, Gauss, Lagrange, Leibnitz, Moser, Sierpinski.

§1. Let A be the set $\{m \in \mathbb{Z} \mid m = \pm p^\beta, \pm 2p^\beta \text{ with } p \text{ an odd prime, } \beta \in N^*, \text{ or } m = \pm 2^\alpha \text{ with } \alpha = 0, 1, 2, \text{ or } m = 0\}$.

Let's consider $m = \varepsilon p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$, with $\varepsilon = \pm 1$, all $\alpha_i \in N^*$, and p_1, \dots, p_s distinct positive numbers.

We construct the FUNCTION $L : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$,

$$L(x, m) = (x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)})$$

where $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)}$ are all residues modulo m relatively prime to m , and φ is the Euler's function.

If all distinct primes which divide x and m simultaneously are $p_{i_1} \dots p_{i_r}$ then:

$$L(x, m) \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \dots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}}},$$

when $m \in A$ respective by $m \notin A$, and

$$L(x, m) \equiv 0 \pmod{m / (p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \dots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}})}.$$

Noting $d = p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \dots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}}$ and $m' = m / d$ we find:

$$L(x, m) \equiv \pm 1 + k_1^0 d \equiv k_2^0 m' \pmod{m}$$

where k_1^0, k_2^0 constitute a particular integer solution of the Diophantine equation $k_2 m' - k_1 d = \pm 1$ (the signs are chosen in accordance with the affiliation of m to A).

This result generalizes the Gauss' theorem ($c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{m}$) when $m \in A$ respectively $m \notin A$ (see [1]) which generalized in its turn the Wilson's theorem (if p is prime then $(p-1)! \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$).

Proof.

The following two lemmas are trivial:

Lemma 1. If $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(p^\alpha)}$ are all residues modulo p^α relatively prime to p^α , with p an integer and $\alpha \in N^*$, then for $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\beta \in N^*$ we have also that $kp^\beta + c_1, \dots, kp^\beta + c_{\varphi(p^\alpha)}$ constitute all residues modulo p^α relatively prime to it is sufficient to prove that for $1 \leq i \leq \varphi(p^\alpha)$ we have that $kp^\beta + c_i$ is relatively prime to p^α , but this is obvious.

Lemma 2. If $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)}$ are all residues modulo m relatively prime to m , $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides m and $p_i^{\alpha_i+1}$ does not divide m , then $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)}$ constitute $\varphi(m / p_i^{\alpha_i})$ systems of all residues modulo $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ relatively prime to $p_i^{\alpha_i}$.

Lemma 3. If $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)}$ are all residues modulo q relatively prime to q and $(b, q) \sim 1$ then $b + c_1, \dots, b + c_{\varphi(m)}$ contain a representative of the class $\hat{0}$ modulo q .

Of course, because $(b, q - b) \sim 1$ there will be a $c_{i_0} = q - b$ whence $b + c_i = \mathbf{M}_q$.

From this we have the following:

Theorem 1. If $\left(x, m / \left(p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \dots p_{i_s}^{\alpha_{i_s}}\right)\right) \sim 1$,

then

$$(x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)}) \equiv 0 \left(\text{mod } m / \left(p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \dots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}} \right) \right).$$

Lemma 4. Because $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{m}$ it results that $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{p_i^{\alpha_i}}$, for all i , when $m \in A$ respectively $m \notin A$.

Lemma 5. If p_i divides x and m simultaneously then:

$$(x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)}) \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{p_i^{\alpha_i}},$$

when $m \in A$ respectively $m \notin A$. Of course, from the lemmas 1 and 2, respectively 4 we have:

$$(x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)}) \equiv c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{p_i^{\alpha_i}}.$$

From the lemma 5 we obtain the following:

Theorem 2. If p_{i_1}, \dots, p_{i_r} are all primes which divide x and m simultaneously then:

$$(x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)}) \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{p_{i_1}^{\alpha_{i_1}} \dots p_{i_r}^{\alpha_{i_r}}},$$

when $m \in A$ respectively $m \notin A$.

From the theorems 1 and 2 it results:

$$L(x, m) \equiv \pm 1 + k_1 d = k_2 m',$$

where $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$. Because $(d, m') \sim 1$ the Diophantine equation $k_2 m' - k_1 d = \pm 1$ admits integer solutions (the unknowns being k_1 and k_2). Hence $k_1 = m' t + k_1^0$ and $k_2 = dt + k_2^0$, with $t \in \mathbb{Z}$, and k_1^0, k_2^0 constitute a particular integer solution of our equation. Thus:

$$L(x, m) \equiv \pm 1 + m' dt + k_1^0 d = \pm 1 + k_1^0 \pmod{m}$$

or

$$L(x, m) = k_2^0 m' \pmod{m}.$$

§2. APPLICATIONS

1) Lagrange extended Wilson's theorem in the following way: "If p is prime then

$$x^{p-1} - 1 \equiv (x+1)(x+2) \dots (x+p-1) \pmod{p}."$$

We shall extend this result as follows: whichever are $m \neq 0, \pm 4$, we have for $x^2 + s^2 \neq 0$ that

$$x^{\varphi(m_s)+s} - x^s \equiv (x+1)(x+2)\dots(x+|m|-1) \pmod{m}$$

where m_s and s are obtained from the algorithm:

$$(0) \quad \begin{cases} x = x_0 d_0; & (x_0, m_0) \sim 1 \\ m = m_0 d_0; & d_0 \neq 1 \end{cases}$$

$$(1) \quad \begin{cases} d_0 = d_0^1 d_1; & (d_0^1, m_1) \sim 1 \\ m_0 = m_1 d_1; & d_1 \neq 1 \end{cases}$$

.....

$$(s-1) \quad \begin{cases} d_{s-2} = d_{s-2}^1 d_{s-1}; & (d_{s-2}^1, m_{s-1}) \sim 1 \\ m_{s-2} = m_{s-1} d_{s-1}; & d_{s-1} \neq 1 \end{cases}$$

$$(s) \quad \begin{cases} d_{s-1} = d_{s-1}^1 d_s; & (d_{s-1}^1, m_s) \sim 1 \\ m_{s-1} = m_s d_s; & d_s \neq 1 \end{cases}$$

(see [3] or [4]). For m positive prime we have $m_s = m$, $s = 0$, and $\varphi(m) = m - 1$, that is Lagrange.

2) L. Moser enunciated the following theorem: If p is prime then $(p-1)!a^p + a = \mathbf{M} p$, and Sierpinski (see [2], p. 57): if p is prime then $a^p + (p-1)!a = \mathbf{M} p$ which merge the Wilson's and Fermat's theorems in a single one.

The function L and the algorithm from §2 will help us to generalize that if " a " and m are integers $m \neq 0$ and $c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)}$ are all residues modulo m relatively prime to m then

$$c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)} a^{\varphi(m_s)+s} - L(0, m) a^s = \mathbf{M} m,$$

respectively

$$-L(0, m) a^{\varphi(m_s)+s} + c_1, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)} a^s = \mathbf{M} m$$

or more:

$$(x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)}) a^{\varphi(m_s)+s} - L(x, m) a^s = \mathbf{M} m$$

respectively

$$-L(x, m) a^{\varphi(m_s)+s} + (x + c_1) \dots (x + c_{\varphi(m)}) a^s = \mathbf{M} m$$

which reunite Fermat, Euler, Wilson, Lagrange and Moser (respectively Sierpinski).

3) A partial spreading of Moser's and Sierpinski's results, the author also obtained (see [6], problem 7.140, pp. 173-174), the following: if m is a positive integer, $m \neq 0, 4$. and " a " is an integer, then $(a^m - a)(m-1)! = \mathbf{M} m$, reuniting Fermat and Wilson in another way.

4) Leibnitz enunciated that: "If p is prime then $(p-2)! \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ ";

We consider " $c_i < c_{i+1} \pmod{m}$ " if $c'_i < c'_{i+1}$ where $0 \leq c'_i < |m|$, $0 \leq c'_{i+1} < |m|$, and $c_i \equiv c'_i \pmod{m}$, $c_{i+1} \equiv c'_{i+1} \pmod{m}$ it seems simply that $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)}$ are all residues modulo m relatively prime to m ($c_i < c_{i+1} \pmod{m}$) for all $i, m \neq 0$, then $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{\varphi(m)-1} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{m}$ if $m \in A$ respectively $m \notin A$, because $c_{\varphi(m)} \equiv -1 \pmod{m}$.

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